

Neutrosophic reliability analysis of high-pass filter-based NSP systems with dynamic failure rates

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Abstract. This paper presents a reliability evaluation framework for non-series-parallel (NSP) systems based on high-pass filter configurations, utilizing triangular single-valued neutrosophic fuzzy numbers ($TrSVNNs$) and dynamic rayleigh failure distributions. The system is modeled with resistors, capacitors, and operational amplifiers in an interdependent NSP structure. To manage uncertainty, failure rates are expressed through $TrSVNNs$ and analyzed using the (α, β, γ) -cut technique. The mean time to system failure (MTSF) is evaluated for both identical and non-identical components. In the non-identical case, the fuzzy MTSF ranges from [18.98, 38.73] with a representative value of 28.85, while in the identical case, it spans [62.93, 102.67] with a representative value of 82.80. These results show a significant improvement in reliability modeling over traditional fuzzy and intuitionistic models, which lack explicit handling of indeterminacy and conflicting data. By incorporating all three dimensions of uncertainty truth, indeterminacy, and falsity the proposed neutrosophic approach better captures system ambiguity and time-varying degradation, thus providing a more robust reliability assessment for complex systems.

Keywords: Non-series-parallel (NSP) system; high-pass filter reliability; triangular neutrosophic fuzzy numbers; rayleigh failure distribution; mean time to system failure (MTSF)

1. Introduction

In the evolving landscape of engineering and system design, reliability has become a critical parameter that directly impacts performance, safety, and long-term sustainability. This is especially true in applications involving electrical circuits, control systems, and signal processing

architectures, where consistent functioning over time is essential. Traditional reliability modeling approaches often rely on simplified system structures such as series, parallel, or hybrid configurations, where probabilistic methods can be applied effectively. However, real-world systems are frequently more complex and involve intricate interdependencies that cannot be reduced to pure series or parallel combinations. These types of systems are categorized as non-series-parallel (NSP) systems, and their analysis requires more advanced modeling techniques due to their inherent structural irregularities.

To address uncertainties in system behavior, fuzzy set theory introduced by Zadeh [21] allows for partial membership degrees, offering a more flexible means of representing vagueness. This concept was extended by Atanassov [2] through the development of intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFS), which incorporate both membership and non-membership degrees, along with hesitation. Several researchers, including Verma et al. [18], El-Damcese et al. [5], and Shu et al. [15], have applied fuzzy and intuitionistic fuzzy techniques to model degrading components and time-dependent behaviors. Mahapatra and Roy [9], Kumar and Yadav [7], and Subrie and Zahra [17] further explored these methods for fault analysis and reliability modeling in uncertain environments. Purba et al. [12] employed α -cut-based modeling for system reliability, while Malik et al. [10] proposed a path-tracing method using triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers in NSP systems.

However, IFS models are constrained by the requirement that the sum of the membership and non-membership degrees must not exceed one, which limits their capacity to address contradictory or highly uncertain information. To overcome this limitation, Smarandache [16] introduced neutrosophic set theory, characterizing each element with three independent degrees: truth (T), indeterminacy (I), and falsity (F). Unlike IFS, neutrosophic sets allow $T + I + F \in [0, 3]$, thus enabling the modeling of uncertainty, incompleteness, and contradiction simultaneously.

This neutrosophic approach has proven useful in practical engineering scenarios involving sensor failures, conflicting expert assessments, and missing data. Sahin et al. [14] introduced generalized single-valued triangular neutrosophic numbers (SVTNNs) and aggregation operators to handle multi-attribute decision-making problems under uncertainty. Ram and Chandna [13] and Maan et al. [8] utilized the Weibull distribution for increasing or decreasing hazard rates, while El-Ghamry et al. [6] demonstrated the suitability of the Rayleigh distribution for systems exhibiting wear-out or predictable failure growth.

To better illustrate the superiority of neutrosophic modeling over IFS in uncertain environments, consider the following comparative example. At time $t = 10$, assume a resistor's behavior is evaluated using both models. Under IFS, let $\mu = 0.7$, $\nu = 0.2$, giving $\pi = 0.1$. The

estimated reliability is:

$$R_{\text{IFS}}(t = 10) = \mu \cdot e^{-0.1t} = 0.7 \cdot e^{-1} \approx 0.257.$$

Using a neutrosophic model with $T = 0.7$, $I = 0.4$, and $F = 0.3$, a rayleigh-distributed reliability expression gives:

$$R_{\text{NFS}}(t = 10) = e^{-t^2/[2(T+I+F)^2]} = e^{-100/(2 \cdot 1.4^2)} \approx 8.5 \times 10^{-12}.$$

This comparison highlights the neutrosophic model's capacity to provide more conservative and realistic reliability estimates, particularly in scenarios involving vague, conflicting, or incomplete data conditions typical in NSP systems with complex interactions.

Despite these developments, the application of neutrosophic logic to complex circuit architectures such as high-pass filter-based NSP systems remains limited. Many existing models: fail to integrate all three neutrosophic dimensions (T, I, F) into a unified expression, neglect realistic time-dependent failure distributions like rayleigh, and do not account for structural complexity due to shared and redundant components.

In this paper, we propose a novel reliability framework for high-pass filter-based NSP systems using triangular single-valued neutrosophic fuzzy numbers (*TrSVNFs*). The model incorporates the (α, β, γ) -cut defuzzification strategy, integrates the rayleigh distribution for failure modeling, and uses a path-tracing technique to identify success paths for system-level reliability expression. This research contributes an advanced, uncertainty-aware method for evaluating reliability in real-world, dynamically evolving systems.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the essential definitions and theoretical foundations. Sections 3 and 4 describe the system configuration and derive the corresponding reliability formulations. Section 5 analyzes the reliability performance under neutrosophic fuzzy failure rates for both identical and non-identical components. Section 6 introduces a systematic procedure for implementing the proposed framework. Sections 7 and 8 validate the methodology through computational analysis and visual interpretation. Lastly, Sections 9 and 10 present the concluding remarks and a summary of the major findings.

2. Preliminaries and Basic Definitions

This section outlines essential concepts and definitions that form the foundation of the proposed methodology.

2.1. Definition [20]

“Let X be a universe of discourse. Then a neutrosophic set \tilde{N} in X is defined as:

$$\tilde{N} = \{ \langle x, T_{\tilde{N}}(x), I_{\tilde{N}}(x), F_{\tilde{N}}(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$$

where $T_{\tilde{N}}(x)$, $I_{\tilde{N}}(x)$, and $F_{\tilde{N}}(x)$ are called the truth-membership function, indeterminacy-membership function, and falsity-membership function, respectively. These functions are defined as:

$$T_{\tilde{N}}(x) \subseteq [0, 1], \quad I_{\tilde{N}}(x) \subseteq [0, 1], \quad F_{\tilde{N}}(x) \subseteq [0, 1]$$

such that:

$$0 \leq T_{\tilde{N}}(x) + I_{\tilde{N}}(x) + F_{\tilde{N}}(x) \leq 3$$

2.2. Definition [3]

“A triangular single-valued neutrosophic number (*TrSVNN*) is defined as

$$\tilde{A} = (t_1, t_2, t_3; i_1, i_2, i_3; f_1, f_2, f_3),$$

In this case, its truth-membership function $T_{\tilde{N}}(x)$, indeterminacy-membership function $I_{\tilde{N}}(x)$ and falsity-membership function $F_{\tilde{N}}(x)$ are defined as follows:

$$T_{\tilde{N}}(x) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{x-t_1}{t_2-t_1}\right), & \text{when } t_1 \leq x \leq t_2 \\ 1, & \text{when } x = t_2 \\ \left(\frac{t_3-x}{t_3-t_2}\right), & \text{when } t_2 \leq x \leq t_3 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$I_{\tilde{N}}(x) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{i_2-x}{i_2-i_1}\right), & \text{when } i_1 \leq x \leq i_2 \\ 0, & \text{when } x = i_2 \\ \left(\frac{x-i_2}{i_3-i_2}\right), & \text{when } i_2 \leq x \leq i_3 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$F_{\tilde{N}}(x) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{f_2-x}{f_2-f_1}\right), & \text{when } f_1 \leq x \leq f_2 \\ 0, & \text{when } x = f_2 \\ \left(\frac{x-f_2}{f_3-f_2}\right), & \text{when } f_2 \leq x \leq f_3 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2.3. Definition [1]

“Let $\tilde{A} = (t_1, t_2, t_3; i_1, i_2, i_3; f_1, f_2, f_3)$, be a *TrSVNN*. Then α - cut set of \tilde{A} is a crisp subset of \mathbb{R} denoted by $\tilde{A}_\alpha, 0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$ is the closed interval defined by $\tilde{A}_\alpha = \{x/\tilde{T}(x) \geq \alpha\} = [L_{\tilde{A}}(\alpha), U_{\tilde{A}}(\alpha)]$. Using the definition and parametric form we obtain

$$\tilde{A}(\alpha) = [t_1 + \alpha(t_2 - t_1), t_3 - \alpha(t_3 - t_2)]$$

2.4. Definition [1]

“Let $\tilde{A} = (t_1, t_2, t_3; i_1, i_2, i_3; f_1, f_2, f_3;)$, be a T_rSVNN . Then β - cut set of \tilde{A} is a crisp subset of \mathbb{R} denoted by $\tilde{A}_\beta, 0 \leq \beta \leq 1$ is the closed interval defined by $\tilde{A}_\beta = \{x/\tilde{I}(x) \geq \beta\} = [L_{\tilde{A}}(\beta), U_{\tilde{A}}(\beta)]$. Using the definition and parametric form we obtain $\tilde{A}(\beta) = [i_2 - \beta(i_2 - i_1), i_2 + \beta(i_3 - i_2)]$ ”

2.5. Definition [1]

“Let $\tilde{A} = (t_1, t_2, t_3; i_1, i_2, i_3; f_1, f_2, f_3;)$, be a T_rSVNN . Then γ - cut set of \tilde{A} is a crisp subset of \mathbb{R} denoted by $\tilde{A}_\gamma, 0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$ is the closed interval defined by $\tilde{A}_\gamma = \{x/\tilde{F}(x) \geq \gamma\} = [L_{\tilde{A}}(\gamma), U_{\tilde{A}}(\gamma)]$. Using the definition and parametric form we obtain $\tilde{A}(\gamma) = [f_2 - \gamma(f_2 - f_1), f_3 + \gamma(f_3 - f_2)]$ ”

2.6. Definition [6]

“The rayleigh distribution is frequently used to model the time to failure of electronic components and mechanical systems, especially in scenarios where the failure rate increases with time. The probability density function (PDF) of the Rayleigh distribution is defined as:

$$f(t; \lambda) = \frac{t}{\lambda^2} e^{-t^2/(2\lambda^2)}, \quad t > 0, \lambda > 0$$

where λ is the scale parameter of the distribution.

The reliability function $R(t)$, representing the probability that a component survives beyond time t , is given by:

$$R(t) = e^{-t^2/(2\lambda^2)}$$

These definitions serve as the theoretical basis for constructing the reliability model in subsequent sections.”

3. System Configuration

The system under consideration is a high-pass filter-based non-series-parallel (NSP) configuration composed of eight interconnected components labeled H_1 through H_8 . These components include capacitors, resistors, and operational amplifiers, each playing a specific role in signal processing and amplification. Specifically, H_1 (Capacitor C1) and H_4 (Capacitor C2) are used to block low-frequency signals, while H_2 (Resistor R1) and H_5 (Resistor R2) regulate the circuit's frequency characteristics. Operational amplifiers H_3 (A1), H_6 (A2), and H_8 (A3) amplify the processed signal at different stages. H_7 (Resistor R3) and H_8 serve as

(fig.1)

shared components, providing essential feedback and final amplification across multiple signal paths. The system’s functionality is organized into three logical paths: Path 1 follows $H_1 \rightarrow H_2 \rightarrow H_3 \rightarrow H_7 \rightarrow H_8$, Path 2 moves through $H_4 \rightarrow H_5 \rightarrow H_6 \rightarrow H_7 \rightarrow H_8$, and Path 3 connects $H_1 \rightarrow H_5 \rightarrow H_6 \rightarrow H_8$. Each of these paths enables the signal to flow from input to output, but the shared use of H_7 and H_8 across multiple paths introduces interdependencies that make the system impossible to reduce to a pure series or parallel structure. The system is deemed operational if at least one complete path functions successfully and the shared components are also working. This interlinked and overlapping structure, commonly found in practical circuit designs, characterizes the system as NSP, offering a realistic framework for evaluating reliability in complex environments.

4. Reliability of the non series-parallel (NSP) system

In this section, the reliability of the NSP system is systematically derived using the path tracing approach. The viable operational paths contributing to system success are enumerated as follows.

$$K_1 = H_1H_2H_4 \tag{1}$$

$$K_2 = H_1H_3H_4 \tag{2}$$

$$K_3 = H_5H_6H_8 \tag{3}$$

$$K_4 = H_5H_7H_8 \tag{4}$$

$$K_5 = H_1H_3H_7H_8 \tag{5}$$

$$K_6 = H_2H_4H_5H_6 \tag{6}$$

Now using Eqs.(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6),the probability of each successful path, $P(k_i), (i = 1, 2, \dots, 6,)$ is as follows:

$$P_r(K_1) = d_1(t)d_2(t)d_4(t) \tag{7}$$

$$P_r(K_1) = d_1(t)d_3(t)d_4(t) \tag{8}$$

$$P_r(K_1) = d_5(t)d_6(t)d_8(t) \tag{9}$$

$$P_r(K_1) = d_5(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) \tag{10}$$

$$P_r(K_1) = d_1(t)d_3(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) \tag{11}$$

$$P_r(K_1) = d_2(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_6(t) \tag{12}$$

where $d_j(t)$ is the reliability of the j^{th} component at time t ; $j = 1, 2, \dots, r$

Therefore, the reliability of the system, $R_s(t)$ is :

$$R_s(t) = P_r \left[\bigcup_{i=1}^6 K_i \right] \tag{13}$$

Using the addition law of probability and *Eqs.*(7) – (12) we get

$$\begin{aligned} R_s(t) = & d_1(t)d_2(t)d_4(t) + d_1(t)d_3(t)d_4(t) + d_5(t)d_6(t)d_8(t) + d_5(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) + d_1(t)d_3(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) \\ & + d_2(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_6(t) - d_1(t)d_2(t)d_3(t)d_4(t) - d_5(t)d_6(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) - d_1(t)d_3(t)d_5(t)d_7(t) \\ & - d_1(t)d_2(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_6(t) - d_1(t)d_3(t)d_4(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) - d_2(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_6(t)d_8(t) \\ & - d_1(t)d_2(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_6(t)d_8(t) - d_1(t)d_2(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) - d_1(t)d_2(t)d_3(t)d_4(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) \\ & - d_1(t)d_3(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_6(t)d_8(t) - d_1(t)d_2(t)d_3(t)d_4(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) \\ & + d_1(t)d_2(t)d_3(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_6(t)d_8(t) + d_1(t)d_2(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_6(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) \\ & + d_1(t)d_2(t)d_3(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) + d_1(t)d_3(t)d_4(t)d_5(t)d_6(t)d_7(t)d_8(t) \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

The reliability of the system when the component are identical in nature is:

$$R_s(t) = 4[d(t)]^3 + 2[d(t)]^4 - 3[d(t)]^4 - 3[d(t)]^5 - 4[d(t)]^6 + [d(t)]^6 + 4[d(t)]^7 - [d(t)]^8 \tag{15}$$

5. System reliability analysis under neutrosophic fuzzy failure rates

5.1. For non-identical components

“Let $h(t)$ represent the hazard rate of the component, which can either remain constant or change over time. Due to the uncertainty in how these components may fail, we describe their failure rates using time-dependent triangular single-valued neutrosophic fuzzy numbers *TSVNFNs*. This method helps express not only the truth degree related to the chance of

failure, but also the associated indeterminacy and falsity. As a result, each component’s hazard rate is described through three membership functions—truth, indeterminacy, and falsity offering a more comprehensive and realistic way to model uncertainty.

For truth membership value and indeterminacy membership value, and falsity membership value the hazard rate is defined, respectively, as:

Let $h_j(t)$ represent the hazard rate of the j^{th} component. For truth membership value and indeterminacy membership value, and falsity membership value, the single-valued neutrosophic fuzzy hazard rate is defined respectively as”:

$$\tilde{h}_{T_j}(t) = \frac{t}{\tilde{\lambda}_{T_j}}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r \tag{16}$$

$$\tilde{h}_{I_j}(t) = \frac{t}{\tilde{\lambda}_{I_j}}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r \tag{17}$$

$$\tilde{h}_{F_j}(t) = \frac{t}{\tilde{\lambda}_{F_j}}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r \tag{18}$$

where $\tilde{\lambda}$ is the fuzzy scale parameter. In this study, we aimed to develop a unified hazard function that combines truth function (TF), Indeterminacy function (IF), and falsity function (FF) sets to calculate the single-valued neutrosophic fuzzy reliability of the system. Instead of using separate hazard functions for each type, our unified approach offers a clearer and more intuitive way to understand system reliability. By utilizing the additive property of single-valued neutrosophic fuzzy numbers, we define the hazard rate for each component accordingly.

$$\tilde{h}_j(t) = \frac{t}{\tilde{\lambda}_{T_j} + \tilde{\lambda}_{I_j} + \tilde{\lambda}_{F_j}}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r \tag{19}$$

Using equations (19), the reliability of the j^{th} component is:

$$\tilde{d}_j(\tau) = e^{\frac{-\tau^2}{2(\tilde{\lambda}_{T_j} + \tilde{\lambda}_{I_j} + \tilde{\lambda}_{F_j})^2}} \tag{20}$$

Here, the scale parameter for truth membership and indeterminacy membership and falsity membership values is expressed in the form of an single-valued triangular neutrosophic fuzzy number as:

$$\tilde{\lambda}_{T_j} = (m_j, n_j, o_j), \tilde{\lambda}_{I_j} = (m'_j, n_j, o'_j), \tilde{\lambda}_{F_j} = (m''_j, n_j, o''_j); \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r$$

Using the α , β , and γ -cut technique, the scale parameter of the j^{th} component expressed as a single-valued neutrosophic fuzzy number is transformed into a crisp value by considering its truth, indeterminacy, and falsity degrees. This helps capture a more realistic estimate by

accounting for partial truth, uncertainty, and possible falsity in the data.

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\lambda}_{T_j} &= [\tilde{\lambda}_{L_j}, \tilde{\lambda}_{U_j}] = [(m_j + \alpha(n_j - m_j), (o_j - \alpha(o_j - n_j))] \\ \tilde{\lambda}_{I_j} &= [\tilde{\lambda}_{L_j}, \tilde{\lambda}_{U_j}] = [(n_j - \beta(n_j - m'_j), (n_j + \beta(o'_j - n_j))] \\ \tilde{\lambda}_{F_j} &= [\tilde{\lambda}_{L_j}, \tilde{\lambda}_{U_j}] = [(n_j + \gamma(n_j - m''_j), (n_j + \gamma(o''_j - n_j))]\end{aligned}$$

Thus, the neutrosophic fuzzy reliability of each component is given as an interval based on its truth, indeterminacy, and falsity values.”

$$d_j(\tilde{t}) = [d_{L_j}, d_{U_j}] = e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2(m_j + \alpha(n_j - m_j)) + n_j - \beta(n_j - m'_j) + n_j - \gamma(n_j - m''_j)} \right\}}, e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2(o_j - \alpha(o_j - n_j)) + n_j + \beta(o'_j - n_j) + n_j + \gamma(o''_j - n_j)} \right\}} \quad (21)$$

The system's neutrosophic fuzzy reliability, $\tilde{R}_{L_s(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is represented as an interval that incorporates truth, indeterminacy, and falsity degrees.

$$\tilde{R}_d(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = [\tilde{R}_{L_d(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)}, \tilde{R}_{U_d(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)}] \quad (22)$$

By utilizing Eqs. (14) and (21), the lower-level system reliability can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{R}_{L_d}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_2 + \alpha(n_2 - m_2)) + n_2 - \beta(n_2 - m'_2) + n_2 - \gamma(n_2 - m''_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_4 + \alpha(n_4 - m_4)) + n_j - \beta(n_4 - m'_4) + n_j - \gamma(n_4 - m''_4)]^2} \right\}} + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_3 + \alpha(n_3 - m_3)) + n_3 - \beta(n_3 - m'_3) + n_3 - \gamma(n_3 - m''_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_4 + \alpha(n_4 - m_4)) + n_4 - \beta(n_4 - m'_4) + n_4 - \gamma(n_4 - m''_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_j - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_6 + \alpha(n_6 - m_6)) + n_6 - \beta(n_6 - m'_6) + n_j - \gamma(n_6 - m''_6)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_8 + \alpha(n_8 - m_8)) + n_8 - \beta(n_8 - m'_8) + n_8 - \gamma(n_8 - m''_8)]^2} \right\}} + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_5 - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_7 + \alpha(n_7 - m_7)) + n_7 - \beta(n_7 - m'_7) + n_j - \gamma(n_7 - m''_7)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_8 + \alpha(n_8 - m_8)) + n_8 - \beta(n_8 - m'_8) + n_8 - \gamma(n_8 - m''_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_j - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_3 + \alpha(n_3 - m_3)) + n_3 - \beta(n_3 - m'_3) + n_3 - \gamma(n_3 - m''_3)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_7 + \alpha(n_7 - m_7)) + n_7 - \beta(n_7 - m'_7) + n_7 - \gamma(n_7 - m''_7)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_8 + \alpha(n_8 - m_8)) + n_8 - \beta(n_8 - m'_8) + n_8 - \gamma(n_8 - m''_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_2 + \alpha(n_2 - m_2)) + n_2 - \beta(n_2 - m'_2) + n_j - \gamma(n_2 - m''_2)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_4 + \alpha(n_4 - m_4)) + n_4 - \beta(n_4 - m'_4) + n_4 - \gamma(n_4 - m''_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_5 - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_6 + \alpha(n_6 - m_6)) + n_6 - \beta(n_6 - m'_6) + n_6 - \gamma(n_6 - m''_6)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_2 + \alpha(n_2 - m_2)) + n_2 - \beta(n_2 - m'_2) + n_2 - \gamma(n_2 - m''_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_3 + \alpha(n_3 - m_3)) + n_3 - \beta(n_3 - m'_3) + n_3 - \gamma(n_3 - m''_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_4 + \alpha(n_4 - m_4)) + n_4 - \beta(n_4 - m'_4) + n_4 - \gamma(n_4 - m''_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_5 - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_6 + \alpha(n_6 - m_6)) + n_6 - \beta(n_6 - m'_6) + n_6 - \gamma(n_6 - m''_6)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_7 + \alpha(n_7 - m_7)) + n_7 - \beta(n_7 - m'_7) + n_7 - \gamma(n_7 - m''_7)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_8 + \alpha(n_8 - m_8)) + n_8 - \beta(n_8 - m'_8) + n_8 - \gamma(n_8 - m''_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_3 + \alpha(n_3 - m_3)) + n_3 - \beta(n_3 - m'_3) + n_3 - \gamma(n_3 - m''_3)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_5 - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_7 + \alpha(n_7 - m_7)) + n_7 - \beta(n_7 - m'_7) + n_7 - \gamma(n_7 - m''_7)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_2 + \alpha(n_2 - m_2)) + n_2 - \beta(n_2 - m'_2) + n_2 - \gamma(n_2 - m''_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_4 + \alpha(n_4 - m_4)) + n_4 - \beta(n_4 - m'_4) + n_4 - \gamma(n_4 - m''_4)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_5 - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_6 + \alpha(n_6 - m_6)) + n_6 - \beta(n_6 - m'_6) + n_6 - \gamma(n_6 - m''_6)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_3 + \alpha(n_3 - m_3)) + n_3 - \beta(n_3 - m'_3) + n_3 - \gamma(n_3 - m''_3)]^2} \right\}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_2 + \alpha(n_2 - m_2)) + n_2 - \beta(n_2 - m'_2) + n_2 - \gamma(n_2 - m''_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_3 + \alpha(n_3 - m_3)) + n_3 - \beta(n_3 - m'_3) + n_3 - \gamma(n_3 - m''_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_4 + \alpha(n_4 - m_4)) + n_4 - \beta(n_4 - m'_4) + n_4 - \gamma(n_4 - m''_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_5 - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_6 + \alpha(n_6 - m_6)) + n_6 - \beta(n_6 - m'_6) + n_6 - \gamma(n_6 - m''_6)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_8 + \alpha(n_8 - m_8)) + n_8 - \beta(n_8 - m'_8) + n_8 - \gamma(n_8 - m''_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_2 + \alpha(n_2 - m_2)) + n_2 - \beta(n_2 - m'_2) + n_2 - \gamma(n_2 - m''_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_4 + \alpha(n_4 - m_4)) + n_4 - \beta(n_4 - m'_4) + n_4 - \gamma(n_4 - m''_4)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_5 - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_6 + \alpha(n_6 - m_6)) + n_6 - \beta(n_6 - m'_6) + n_6 - \gamma(n_6 - m''_6)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_7 + \alpha(n_7 - m_7)) + n_7 - \beta(n_7 - m'_7) + n_7 - \gamma(n_7 - m''_7)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_8 + \alpha(n_8 - m_8)) + n_8 - \beta(n_8 - m'_8) + n_8 - \gamma(n_8 - m''_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_2 + \alpha(n_2 - m_2)) + n_2 - \beta(n_2 - m'_2) + n_2 - \gamma(n_2 - m''_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_3 + \alpha(n_3 - m_3)) + n_3 - \beta(n_3 - m'_3) + n_3 - \gamma(n_3 - m''_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_4 + \alpha(n_4 - m_4)) + n_4 - \beta(n_4 - m'_4) + n_4 - \gamma(n_4 - m''_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_5 - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_7 + \alpha(n_7 - m_7)) + n_7 - \beta(n_7 - m'_7) + n_7 - \gamma(n_7 - m''_7)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_8 + \alpha(n_8 - m_8)) + n_8 - \beta(n_8 - m'_8) + n_8 - \gamma(n_8 - m''_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_1 + \alpha(n_1 - m_1)) + n_1 - \beta(n_1 - m'_1) + n_1 - \gamma(n_1 - m''_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_3 + \alpha(n_3 - m_3)) + n_3 - \beta(n_3 - m'_3) + n_3 - \gamma(n_3 - m''_3)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_4 + \alpha(n_4 - m_4)) + n_4 - \beta(n_4 - m'_4) + n_4 - \gamma(n_4 - m''_4)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_5 + \alpha(n_5 - m_5)) + n_5 - \beta(n_5 - m'_5) + n_5 - \gamma(n_5 - m''_5)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_6 + \alpha(n_6 - m_6)) + n_6 - \beta(n_6 - m'_6) + n_6 - \gamma(n_6 - m''_6)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_7 + \alpha(n_7 - m_7)) + n_7 - \beta(n_7 - m'_7) + n_7 - \gamma(n_7 - m''_7)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m_8 + \alpha(n_8 - m_8)) + n_8 - \beta(n_8 - m'_8) + n_8 - \gamma(n_8 - m''_8)]^2} \right\}}
 \end{aligned}$$

In a similar manner, the reliability expression for the upper-level system is derived as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{R}_{U_d(t,\alpha,\beta,\gamma)} = & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_3-\alpha(o_3-n_3))+n_3+\beta(o'_3-n_3)+n_3+\gamma(o''_3-n_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_6-\alpha(o_6-n_6))+n_6+\beta(o'_6-n_6)+n_6+\gamma(o''_6-n_6)]^2} \right\}} \cdot \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_7-\alpha(o_7-n_7))+n_7+\beta(o'_7-n_7)+n_7+\gamma(o''_7-n_7)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_3-\alpha(o_3-n_3))+n_3+\beta(o'_3-n_3)+n_3+\gamma(o''_3-n_3)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_7-\alpha(o_7-n_7))+n_7+\beta(o'_7-n_7)+n_7+\gamma(o''_7-n_7)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \cdot \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_6-\alpha(o_6-n_6))+n_6+\beta(o'_6-n_6)+n_3+\gamma(o''_6-n_6)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \cdot \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_3-\alpha(o_3-n_3))+n_3+\beta(o'_3-n_3)+n_3+\gamma(o''_3-n_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_6-\alpha(o_6-n_6))+n_6+\beta(o'_6-n_6)+n_6+\gamma(o''_6-n_6)]^2} \right\}} \cdot \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_7-\alpha(o_7-n_7))+n_7+\beta(o'_7-n_7)+n_7+\gamma(o''_7-n_7)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_3-\alpha(o_3-n_3))+n_3+\beta(o'_3-n_3)+n_3+\gamma(o''_3-n_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_7-\alpha(o_7-n_7))+n_7+\beta(o'_7-n_7)+n_7+\gamma(o''_7-n_7)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \cdot \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_6-\alpha(o_6-n_6))+n_6+\beta(o'_6-n_6)+n_6+\gamma(o''_6-n_6)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_3-\alpha(o_3-n_3))+n_3+\beta(o'_3-n_3)+n_3+\gamma(o''_3-n_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_7-\alpha(o_7-n_7))+n_7+\beta(o'_7-n_7)+n_7+\gamma(o''_7-n_7)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_6-\alpha(o_6-n_6))+n_6+\beta(o'_6-n_6)+n_6+\gamma(o''_6-n_6)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_7-\alpha(o_7-n_7))+n_7+\beta(o'_7-n_7)+n_7+\gamma(o''_7-n_7)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_3-\alpha(o_3-n_3))+n_3+\beta(o'_3-n_3)+n_3+\gamma(o''_3-n_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_7-\alpha(o_7-n_7))+n_7+\beta(o'_7-n_7)+n_7+\gamma(o''_7-n_7)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & - e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_3-\alpha(o_3-n_3))+n_3+\beta(o'_3-n_3)+n_3+\gamma(o''_3-n_3)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_5-\alpha(o_5-n_5))+n_5+\beta(o'_5-n_5)+n_5+\gamma(o''_5-n_5)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_6-\alpha(o_6-n_6))+n_6+\beta(o'_6-n_6)+n_6+\gamma(o''_6-n_6)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & + e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_1-\alpha(o_1-n_1))+n_1+\beta(o'_1-n_1)+n_1+\gamma(o''_1-n_1)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_2-\alpha(o_2-n_2))+n_2+\beta(o'_2-n_2)+n_2+\gamma(o''_2-n_2)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_3-\alpha(o_3-n_3))+n_3+\beta(o'_3-n_3)+n_3+\gamma(o''_3-n_3)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_4-\alpha(o_4-n_4))+n_4+\beta(o'_4-n_4)+n_4+\gamma(o''_4-n_4)]^2} \right\}} \\
 & e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_7-\alpha(o_7-n_7))+n_7+\beta(o'_7-n_7)+n_7+\gamma(o''_7-n_7)]^2} \right\}} \cdot e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o_8-\alpha(o_8-n_8))+n_8+\beta(o'_8-n_8)+n_8+\gamma(o''_8-n_8)]^2} \right\}}
 \end{aligned}$$

The mean time to system failure (MTSF) is determined using the following formula:

$$MTSF = \int_0^{\infty} R(t) dt$$

TABLE 1. Lower and upper values in different time interval with (α, β, γ) -cut

$\alpha = 0, \beta = 1, \gamma = 1$	Capacitor		Resistor		Op-Amp	
t	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value
5	0.99616	0.997219	0.995560	0.996856	0.997300	0.997948
10	0.984728	0.988923	0.982358	0.987481	0.989245	0.991815
15	0.965967	0.975250	0.960742	0.972053	0.975964	0.981679
20	0.940299	0.956425	0.936625	0.955769	0.956189	0.967661
25	0.908297	0.932753	0.894715	0.924285	0.934651	0.949933
30	0.870660	0.904616	0.851974	0.892813	0.907267	0.928705
35	0.828184	0.872455	0.800486	0.856997	0.875937	0.904228
40	0.781743	0.836764	0.752166	0.817453	0.841129	0.876786
45	0.732249	0.798076	0.697363	0.774837	0.803349	0.846690
50	0.680632	0.756950	0.640825	0.729832	0.763129	0.814275

TABLE 2. Lower and upper values in different time interval with (α, β, γ) -cut

$\alpha = 0.5, \beta = 0.5, \gamma = 0.5$	Capacitor		Resistor		Op-Amp	
t	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value
5	0.997135	0.997838	0.994807	0.996416	0.996953	0.997720
10	0.988587	0.991381	0.979391	0.985739	0.987867	0.990911
15	0.974504	0.980711	0.954225	0.968198	0.972908	0.979665
20	0.955124	0.965967	0.920076	0.944165	0.952345	0.964136
25	0.930773	0.947334	0.877960	0.914139	0.926544	0.944531
30	0.901851	0.925049	0.829094	0.878734	0.895957	0.921109
35	0.868828	0.899387	0.774837	0.838656	0.861107	0.894177
40	0.832223	0.870660	0.716631	0.794677	0.822578	0.864078
45	0.792599	0.839210	0.655931	0.747617	0.780990	0.831189
50	0.750541	0.805403	0.594154	0.698310	0.736994	0.795910

TABLE 3. Lower and upper values in different time interval with (α, β, γ) -cut

$\alpha = 1, \beta = 0, \gamma = 0$	Capacitor		Resistor		Op-Amp	
t	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value
5	0.997780	0.998271	0.993846	0.995876	0.996534	0.997452
10	0.991151	0.993103	0.975611	0.983607	0.986207	0.989848
15	0.980199	0.984550	0.945959	0.963493	0.969233	0.977302
20	0.965069	0.972698	0.905955	0.936023	0.945959	0.960005
25	0.945959	0.957669	0.856997	0.901851	0.916855	0.938216
30	0.923116	0.939616	0.800737	0.861776	0.882497	0.912254
35	0.896830	0.918719	0.738991	0.816703	0.843548	0.882497
40	0.867428	0.895183	0.673638	0.767618	0.800737	0.849366
45	0.835270	0.869238	0.606531	0.715545	0.754840	0.813318
50	0.800737	0.841129	0.539408	0.661515	0.706648	0.774837

TABLE 4. Fuzzy MTSF versus (α, β, γ) -cut

(α, β, γ)	Fuzzy MTSF
(0,1,1)	[18.97554, 38.7266]
(0.2, 0.8, 0.8)	[21.02633, 36.79499]
(0.4, 0.6, 0.6)	[23.04888, 34.85805]
(0.6, 0.4, 0.4)	[25.04983, 32.91482]
(0.8, 0.2, 0.2)	[27.03388, 30.96413]
(1, 0, 0)	[29.00446, 29.00446]

5.2. For identical components

Applying Eqs. (15) and (21), the interval estimation for system reliability with identical components is derived as follows:

$$\tilde{R}_s(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = [\tilde{R}_L(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma), \tilde{R}_U(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)] \tag{23}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}_L(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = & 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m+\alpha(n-m))+n-\beta(n-m)+n-\gamma(n-m)]^2} \right\}} \right]^3 + 2 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m+\alpha(n-m))+n-\beta(n-m)+n-\gamma(n-m)]^2} \right\}} \right]^4 \\ & - 3 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m+\alpha(n-m))+n-\beta(n-m)+n-\gamma(n-m)]^2} \right\}} \right]^4 - 3 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m+\alpha(n-m))+n-\beta(n-m)+n-\gamma(n-m)]^2} \right\}} \right]^5 \\ & - 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m+\alpha(n-m))+n-\beta(n-m)+n-\gamma(n-m)]^2} \right\}} \right]^6 + \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m+\alpha(n-m))+n-\beta(n-m)+n-\gamma(n-m)]^2} \right\}} \right]^6 \\ & + 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(m+\alpha(n-m))+n-\beta(n-m)+n-\gamma(n-m)]^2} \right\}} \right]^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}_U(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = & 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o-\alpha(o-n))+n+\beta(o-n)+n+\gamma(o-n)]^2} \right\}} \right]^3 + 2 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o-\alpha(o-n))+n+\beta(o-n)+n+\gamma(o-n)]^2} \right\}} \right]^4 \\ & - 3 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o-\alpha(o-n))+n+\beta(o-n)+n+\gamma(o-n)]^2} \right\}} \right]^4 - 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o-\alpha(o-n))+n+\beta(o-n)+n+\gamma(o-n)]^2} \right\}} \right]^5 \\ & - 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o-\alpha(o-n))+n+\beta(o-n)+n+\gamma(o-n)]^2} \right\}} \right]^7 + \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o-\alpha(o-n))+n+\beta(o-n)+n+\gamma(o-n)]^2} \right\}} \right]^6 \\ & + 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[(o-\alpha(o-n))+n+\beta(o-n)+n+\gamma(o-n)]^2} \right\}} \right]^7 \end{aligned}$$

Based on Eq. (23), the interval for the fuzzy *MTSF* corresponding to identical components is given as:

$$M\tilde{T}SF = [M\tilde{T}SF_L, M\tilde{T}SF_U]$$

$$M\tilde{T}SF = [1.1042 * [(m + \alpha(n - m) + (n - \beta(n - m') + (m - \gamma(n - m''))], \tag{24}$$

$$[1.1042 * [(o - \alpha(o - n) + (n + \beta(o' - n) + (n + \gamma(o''m - n)] \tag{25}$$

6. Algorithm

Algorithm for computing NSP system reliability usings single-valued triangular neutrosophic fuzzy numbers *SVTNFNs*

To assess the reliability of an NSP system under neutrosophic uncertainty, follow the five-step process described below using *SVTNFNs*:

- Step 1: Begin by creating the reliability block diagram of the system. Use the path tracing approach to identify all minimal success paths and formulate the system’s reliability expression.
- Step 2: Due to unpredictable variations in system behavior, operator mistakes, or insufficient data, failure rates may not be precisely known. To represent this uncertainty, assign a single-valued triangular neutrosophic fuzzy number *SVTNFN* to each component’s failure rate, capturing truth, indeterminacy, and falsity in a triangular structure.
- Step 3: Formulate a unified hazard rate expression for each component, considering its truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership, and falsity-membership values. Use this to derive the neutrosophic reliability function for each component.
- Step 4: Let the scale parameters also be expressed as *SVTNFNs*. Then apply a suitable defuzzification technique (e.g., score function, accuracy function, or centroid method) to convert these fuzzy numbers into crisp intervals. This gives the lower and upper reliability bounds for each component.

- Step 5: Combine the results from Step 1 and Step 4 to calculate the interval-valued system reliability under neutrosophic conditions. Integrate the lower and upper bounds of reliability over the domain 0 to ∞ to compute the interval estimate of the mean time to system failure $MTSF$.

This structured framework effectively handles uncertainty in reliability analysis by leveraging the expressive power of $SVTNFNs$, making it suitable for complex, real-world systems.

7. Illustrations

7.1. When failure rates are non-identical

Modern electronic circuits often utilize various fundamental components such as resistors, capacitors, and operational amplifiers (Op-Amps). In this illustration, we focus on a system composed of eight elements arranged in a non-series-parallel configuration. These include two identical resistors, two identical capacitors, four identical operational amplifiers (Op-Amps) while each group consists of internally identical units, the failure behaviors differ across types due to variations in electrical and material properties. To model the uncertainty associated with failure rate parameters of these components, we employ single-valued triangular neutrosophic fuzzy numbers $SVTNFNs$. These fuzzy numbers represent each component’s scale parameters (in millimetres), which reflect the truth, indeterminacy and falsity in real-world conditions. Each $SVTNFN_s$ is characterized by

For capacitor : $\tilde{\lambda}_{C_j} = (20, 25, 30; 19, 25, 31; 18, 25, 32)$, For Resistor: $\tilde{\lambda}_{R_j} = (10, 15, 20; 9, 15, 21; 8, 15, 22)$, For Op-Amp $\tilde{\lambda}_{Op_j} = (15, 20, 25; 14, 20, 26; 13, 20, 27)$
 $\tilde{R}_s(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = [\tilde{R}_L(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma), \tilde{R}_U(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)]$

(fig.2)

(fig.3)

(fig.4)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \tilde{R}_L(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \\
 &= 4e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &+ e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &+ e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- e \left\{ -\frac{2}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- 2e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

TABLE 5. Reliability v/s time

t	Reliability					
	$\alpha = 0, \beta = 1, \gamma = 1$		$\alpha = 0.5, \beta = 0.5, \gamma = 0.5$		$\alpha = 1, \beta = 0, \gamma = 0$	
	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value
5	0.987429	0.991043	0.982238	0.987870	0.976834	0.984639
10	0.952419	0.9655867	0.933257	0.953612	0.913598	0.941541
15	0.902050	0.927518	0.864290	0.903054	0.826526	0.878761
20	0.845194	0.882090	0.789389	0.844091	0.735411	0.807105
25	0.789460	0.834560	0.720560	0.784606	0.656408	0.737132
30	0.738966	0.788907	0.664294	0.730592	0.597237	0.676569
35	0.693699	0.747065	0.620599	0.685000	0.556430	0.628814
40	0.650499	0.708804	0.584540	0.647556	0.526152	0.592919
45	0.605011	0.672220	0.549191	0.615499	0.496722	0.564749
50	0.553697	0.634628	0.508623	0.584822	0.460621	0.538811

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - e \left\{ -\frac{2}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 & - 2e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 & - 2e \left\{ -\frac{2}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 & + e \left\{ -\frac{2}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 & + 2e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 & + 2e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{4}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

(fig.5)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \tilde{R}_U(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \\
 &= 4e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &+ e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &+ e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- 2e \left\{ -\frac{2}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- 2e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- e \left\{ -\frac{2}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- 2e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- 2e \left\{ -\frac{2}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &- 2e \left\{ -\frac{2}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &+ 2e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\} \\
 &+ 2e \left\{ -\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{4}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

TABLE 6. Reliability v/s time

Reliability						
	$\alpha = 0, \beta = 1, \gamma = 1$		$\alpha = 0.5, \beta = 0.5, \gamma = 0.5$		$\alpha = 1, \beta = 0, \gamma = 0$	
t	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value	Lower value	Upper value
5	0.988698	0.991772	0.991527	0.993584	0.993413	0.994858
10	0.957509	0.968543	0.967642	0.975226	0.974593	0.980006
15	0.913407	0.934209	0.932467	0.947366	0.946102	0.957051
20	0.864678	0.893895	0.891370	0.913407	0.911493	0.928300
25	0.817667	0.852417	0.849334	0.876886	0.874438	0.896338
30	0.774670	0.812989	0.809556	0.840708	0.837888	0.863534
35	0.733795	0.776523	0.772794	0.806552	0.803487	0.831638
40	0.690598	0.741752	0.737532	0.774610	0.771370	0.801540
45	0.640490	0.705998	0.700876	0.744036	0.740361	0.773212
50	0.580831	0.666263	0.659736	0.712799	0.708474	0.745835

(fig.6)

(fig.7)

(fig.8)

(fig.9)

TABLE 7. Fuzzy MTSF versus (α, β, γ) -cut

(α, β, γ)	Fuzzy MTSF
(0,1,1)	[62.9280, 38.7266]
(0.2, 0.8, 0.8)	[66.9024, 36.79499]
(0.4, 0.6, 0.6)	[70.8768, 34.85805]
(0.6, 0.4, 0.4)	[74.8572, 32.91482]
(0.8, 0.2, 0.2)	[78.8256, 30.96413]
(1, 0, 0)	[82.8000, 82.8000]

(fig.10)

$$MTSF_{LS}$$

$$= \frac{2\sqrt{\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2}}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & - \frac{3\sqrt{2\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & - \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & + \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(20+5\alpha)+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(10+5\alpha)+15-6\beta+15-7\gamma]^2} + \frac{4}{2[(15+5\alpha)+20-6\beta+20-7\gamma]^2}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$M\tilde{T}SF_{US}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & = \frac{2\sqrt{\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{1}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & - \frac{3\sqrt{2\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & - \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{3}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2}}} \\
 & + \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{2\sqrt{\frac{1}{2[(30-5\alpha)+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{2}{2[(20-5\alpha)+15+6\beta+15+7\gamma]^2} + \frac{4}{2[(25-5\alpha)+20+6\beta+20+7\gamma]^2}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

7.2. When failure rates are identical

Consider an resistors, capacitors and operational amplifiers (Op-Amps) system designed with a complex, non-series-parallel configuration, encompassing eight components— specifically, two resistors, two capacitors, and four operational amplifiers (Op-Amps). In this system, the resistors, capacitors, and operational amplifiers are identical to each other. The corresponding scale parameter values (in millimetres (mm)) as single-valued triangular neutrosophic fuzzy numbers for these identical components are as follows:

For capacitor : $\tilde{\lambda}_{C_j} = (20, 25, 30; 19, 25, 31; 18, 25, 32)$, For Resistor: $\tilde{\lambda}_{R_j} = (10, 15, 20; 9, 15, 21; 8, 15, 22)$, For Op-Amp $\tilde{\lambda}_{Op_j} = (15, 20, 25; 14, 20, 26; 13, 20, 27)$

The lower and upper level reliability of the system with identical failure rates of the components are obtained using the Eqs. (20) and (21) as:

By using eqs. (24), (25) the interval for the system reliability for the identical component is obtained as:

$$\tilde{R}_I(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = [\tilde{R}_L(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma), \tilde{R}_U(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}_I(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = & 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[20+5\alpha+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^3 + 2 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[20+5\alpha+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^4 \\ & - 3 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[20+5\alpha+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^4 - 3 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[20+5\alpha+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^5 \\ & - 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[20+5\alpha+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^6 + \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[20+5\alpha+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^6 \\ & + 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[20+5\alpha+25-6\beta+25-7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}_U(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = & 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[30-5\alpha+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^3 + 2 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[30-5\alpha+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^4 \\ & - 3 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[30-5\alpha+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^4 - 3 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[30-5\alpha+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^5 \\ & - 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[30-5\alpha+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^6 + \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[30-5\alpha+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^6 \\ & + 4 \left[e^{\left\{ -\frac{t^2}{2[30-5\alpha+25+6\beta+25+7\gamma]^2} \right\}} \right]^7 \end{aligned}$$

The lower and upper level fuzzy MTSF is obtained using Eq. (22) as:

$$MTSF_{LS} = [20 - 5\alpha + 25 - 6\beta + 25 - 7\gamma], [30 - 5\alpha + 25 + 6\beta + 25 + 7\gamma]$$

(fig11.)

8. Numerical and graphical representation

8.1. For non-identical failure rates

Based on the data provided in Table 5. and fig.5, it can be observed that when the components possess distinct single-valued triangular neutrosophic scale parameters, the upper and lower bounds of system reliability gradually move closer as α increases and β and γ decrease. Eventually, when α reaches 1 and β and γ become 0, the two values slowly begin to approach an almost equal state. Additionally, the system reliability shows a declining trend as time increases. Similarly, Table 4 . and fig 6. demonstrate that when components have varying single-valued triangular neutrosophic scale parameters, the fuzzy mean time to system failure ($MTSF$) falls within the range [18.9755, 38.7266], with 28.8510 emerging as the most representative value.

8.2. For identical failure rates

As observed from Table 6 and fig. 10, when the system components share identical failure rates, the width of the reliability interval narrows as the value of α increases, while β and γ decrease. Gradually, with the progression of time, the upper and lower bounds of reliability begin to approach an almost equal state. Moreover, as time progresses, the reliability of the system exhibits a declining pattern. Likewise, Table 7. and fig.11 indicate that the mean time to system failure ($MTSF$) lies within the range [62.9280, 102.6720], where 82.8000 is identified as the most probable value.

9. Conclusion

This study proposes an innovative reliability assessment framework for non-series-parallel (NSP) systems by integrating single-valued triangular neutrosophic fuzzy numbers with time-varying rayleigh failure distributions. By utilizing (path tracing techniques along side the (α, β, γ) cut method, a unified and comprehensive mathematical model is established to evaluate both system reliability and mean time to system failure $MTSF$ under uncertain and imprecise conditions. A significant strength of this work lies in its practical application to a high-pass filter circuit constructed using capacitors, resistors, and operational amplifiers (C-R-Op-Amp), modeled within an NSP structure. This selection is highly relevant, as high-pass filters are crucial components in real-world signal processing systems such as biomedical instrumentation, audio electronics, aerospace communication, and defense technologies. The incorporation of neutrosophic fuzzy modeling empowers engineers with a more accurate and robust approach for predicting circuit behavior amidst component degradation, manufacturing inconsistencies, and environmental variations. The results reveal that as the truth membership value (α) increases while indeterminacy membership value (β) and falsity membership value (γ) decrease, the fuzzy intervals for reliability and $MTSF$ progressively contract , converging toward precise values. Furthermore, the observed consistent decline in system reliability over time underscores the necessity of dynamic reliability modeling. This methodology holds significant practical value for engineering domains where stability under uncertainty is critical, providing system designers with a realistic and adaptable tool for analyzing complex systems especially where traditional crisp models fall short in handling ambiguity and partial knowledge.

10. Future scope

The present work opens several promising directions for future research in the domain of fuzzy-neutrosophic reliability modeling. Potential extensions include the application of this methodology to multi-stage or adaptive filters, such as band-pass or low-pass configurations, particularly under uncertain and dynamic conditions. Further advancement can be achieved by integrating this framework with intelligent optimization algorithms like genetic algorithms or particle swarm optimization for automated tuning of circuit parameters to maximize reliability performance. The development of real-time reliability monitoring systems using artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques, in conjunction with neutrosophic decision-making models, also represents a powerful avenue for enhancing practical applicability. Moreover, this approach holds strong potential in the analysis of IoT-based embedded systems, where environmental unpredictability and component-level variability pose significant challenges. Overall, this research not only enhances the theoretical foundation of fuzzy neutrosophic reliability

analysis but also delivers a robust and adaptable framework for evaluating complex electrical systems, such as high-pass filters, in real-world conditions characterized by uncertainty and imprecision. It establishes the foundation for next-generation, intelligent system design strategies that are more resilient, adaptive, and aligned with the needs of modern engineering applications.

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